

CoARA Core Documents Update Procedure

Version: 2.0

Published: 04 October 2023 (draft circulated among the CoARA members)

HISTORY OF CHANGE

Version	Date	Page	Change
1.0	20/10/2022		Initial version
2.0	27/09/2023	1. & 2	<p>Timeframes were added in response to request for modification initiated by CoARA member at the first General Assembly.</p> <p>On page 1 the paragraph</p> <p>“This request may be addressed at any point but no later than 30 calendar days before the General Assembly that will be asked to vote on this request.”</p> <p>was changed to</p> <p>“This request may be addressed at any point but no later than 44 calendar days before the General Assembly that will be asked to vote on this request. ”</p> <p>On page 2 the paragraph</p> <p>“The request and Steering Board’s position (if any) will be circulated to CoARA members no later than 14 calendar days before the General Assembly meeting discussing the modification.”</p> <p>was changed to:</p> <p>“The request and Steering Board’s position (if any) will be circulated to CoARA members no later than 30 calendar days before the General Assembly meeting discussing the modification. ”</p>

Introduction

The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment ([CoARA](#)) activities and development framework is described in a set of core documents that have been endorsed by the CoARA General Assembly. As of 1st June 2023, these documents are:

- CoARA Governance Document, adopted by the CoARA constitutive Assembly on 1st December 2022.
- CoARA Code of Conduct, adopted by the CoARA constitutive Assembly on 1st December 2022.
- CoARA Rules of Procedure Chair, Vice-Chair(s) and Steering Board, adopted by the CoARA constitutive Assembly on 1st December 2022.
- CoARA Rules of Procedure Working Groups, adopted by the CoARA constitutive Assembly on 1st December 2022.

This list will evolve and will be updated by the CoARA secretariat.

Updating CoARA Core documentation

CoARA members or the CoARA Steering Board may propose updates or evolution in the CoARA core documentation. As these documents have been approved by the Coalition's General Assembly, only the General Assembly can eventually decide on their modification. Updating CoARA's core documentation will require to go through the following procedure:

Request for modification initiated by a CoARA member:

- The authorised representative of a CoARA member writes to the CoARA Chairperson and the CoARA secretariat to express their intent to modify one of the CoARA core documents, indicating:
 - o what document should be modified,
 - o what are the rationale behind the request for modification,
 - o what part(s) of the document should be modified,
 - o what new wording should be used,
 - o (if relevant) other CoARA members backing the suggestion for modification.
- This request may be addressed at any point but no later than 44 calendar days before the General Assembly that will be asked to vote on this request
- The request will be put on the agenda of the CoARA General Assembly. The CoARA

Steering Board will review the request and may express its views and/or a recommendation for the General Assembly vote.

- The request and Steering Board's position (if any) will be circulated to CoARA members no later than 30 calendar days before the General Assembly meeting discussing the modification.
- The General Assembly will be asked to vote on the suggested modification and proposed new wording. Two-thirds majority will be required to approve and adopt the new wording.'

In case of more than one request for change on the same piece of text is put to the vote, the option with the highest number of votes will be implemented.

- The CoARA secretariat will update the document in line with the decision of the General Assembly. It will archive the outdated version of the document and circulate the new one.

Request for modification initiated by the CoARA Steering Board:

- If the Steering Board wishes to propose a modification of a core document, it will compile a document indicating:
 - o what document should be modified,
 - o what are the rationale behind the request for modification,
 - o what part(s) of the document should be modified,
 - o what new wording should be used,
- The proposition will be circulated to CoARA members no later than 14 calendar days before the General Assembly meeting discussing the modification..
- The General Assembly will be asked to vote on the suggested modification and proposed new wording. The majority (more than half) of vote will be required to adopt the new wording.
- In case of more than one request for change on the same piece of text is put to the vote, the option with the highest number of votes will be implemented.
- The CoARA secretariat will update the document in line with the decision of the General Assembly. It will archive the outdated version of the document and circulate the new one.